

MEDICAL SCIENCES

RESTORATION OF THE INTEGRITY OF THE DENTITION WITH FIXED PROSTHESES SUPPORTED BY DENTAL IMPLANTS

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Abstract

An alternative to orthopedic treatment of partial and complete adentia is prosthetics on dental implants. The development of methods is on the way to reduce trauma, reduce costs, reduce the waiting time for the end of treatment and increase the service life of structures. The aim of this study was to analyze the effectiveness of prosthetics on implants in partial and complete adentia. The object of the study were 92 patients with partial or complete adentia.

Prosthetics was carried out after the method of one-stage or two-stage implantation of implants. The development of methods of prosthetics on implants is on the way to reduce trauma, reduce costs, reduce the waiting time for the end of treatment and increase the service life of structures.

Keywords: adentia, dental implants, prosthetics.

The treatment of people suffering from adentia is not only an urgent interdisciplinary task of therapeutic, orthopedic and surgical dentistry, but also a social problem. The tasks of rehabilitation should be considered: restoration of the function of chewing and speech; prevention of atrophy and osteoporosis of the jaws; the maximum possible reduction in the terms of functional adaptation of patients to dentures;

One of the urgent problems of modern dentistry is the restoration of the functional and aesthetic parameters of the dentoalveolar system with partial loss of teeth in the absence of the possibility of manufacturing standard fixed structures of dentures. In such cases, fixed prostheses are made based on dental implants. The results of the study showed that the designs of fixed prostheses with fixation on implants are more prognostically favorable for the preservation of periodontal tissues.

The mass susceptibility of the modern population to such dental diseases as caries and periodontitis leads to the loss of a significant number of teeth, starting from an early age. An analysis of the data on the frequency of occurrence of defects in the dentition in the adult population showed that partial and complete secondary adentia occurs in 61.8% of the examined patients. At the same time, the largest percentage of missing teeth by group affiliation was molars (60.3%). The appearance of defects in the dentition contributes to the violation of its integrity, and hence the performance of functions, including chewing and aesthetic [1, 6]. Restoration of dentition is most often carried out by orthopedic or not carried out at all. The objective reasons for the latter fact can be considered the fear of extensive interventions, the unwillingness to "grind" healthy teeth, and the insufficient duration of the use of prostheses. Currently, methods are being used and improved that

can constitute an alternative to orthopedic prosthetics. Designs on implants implanted into the alveolar bone are becoming increasingly popular [2, 7].

Despite the vast number of publications that still consider various aspects of the theory and practice of implantology, there are still little-studied issues that require

answers. In particular, data on the need for such treatment in certain age groups, the frequency of errors and complications are poorly covered. There is clearly insufficient information about the role of the dental therapist in the preparation and management of patients with implants and subsequent prosthetics [1, 5]. A number of people with removable dentures in the oral cavity refuse to perform two-stage implantation, which is performed in several surgical stages and requires a long waiting time, usually 6 months or more [5, 8]. The method of one-stage implantation with immediate loading allows the patient to install implants and non-removable orthopedic structures without the use of bone tissue augmentation and sinus lift, directly into the sockets of the extracted teeth after their removal. Prosthetics is carried out within 3–7 days after surgery [3, 4]. At the same time, advanced age is not a contraindication to this type of implantation. The aim of this study was to analyze the effectiveness of prosthetics on implants in partial and complete adentia.

Materials and methods. The object of the study were 52 patients who underwent implantation operations in a surgical room, followed by the installation of fixed prostheses. A total of 142 implants were implanted. One-stage implantation was performed in 32 patients with 92 implants integrated, two-stage implantation was performed in 20 patients, 50 implants were integrated. With partial adentia, the included defects of

the dentition amounted to 43.7%, terminal - 56.3%. Determination of indications for the choice of treatment method in each case was carried out after a diagnostic assessment: anamnesis (general, special); examination of soft and hard tissues; assessment of dental and periodontal status; functional diagnostics; model analysis; radiography. The causes of tooth loss (caries, periodontal disease, trauma, tumor) were studied; prognosis of implant intervention depending on the cause of tooth loss; prognostic assessment of the teeth preserved in the occlusion and their orthopedic significance in combination with the prognosis of implantation. A general treatment plan was drawn up. The orthopedic treatment plan is focused on the restoration of lost structures, functions and aesthetics; prevention of the progression of pathological processes; preservation of existing tissue structures (hard tissues of teeth, bone, soft tissues); long-term functional usefulness of the orthopedic structure; the possibility of expanding the prosthetic structure in the future. Since the life of implants depends to a large extent on the hygienic state of the oral cavity, an important role was given to training in individual hygiene. Self-care products for implant patients can make plaque removal much easier. The main means of self-hygiene is a soft toothbrush, and it can be either manual or mechanical. Interdental plaque can be removed with regular dental floss (floss, superfloss), nylon floss, monobundle brush or other devices that can also be passed under the denture and remove plaque around the abutments. Irrigators (in low power mode) facilitate the removal of food debris from under and around the denture. Antimicrobial mouthwashes (such as chlorhexidine) can reduce supragingival plaque formation. To clean implants, it is not recommended to use pastes, rinses and deodorants for the oral cavity containing chlorine in an ionized state - halogen-containing toothpastes. For professional oral hygiene in the area of implants, the least abrasive methods for removing dental deposits were used. For manual removal of deposits, curettes and scalers were used, the working parts of which were made of plastic, nylon, or special alloys. The choice of design was influenced by the volume of the preserved bone, the contours of the alveolar ridge, and the proposed location of the implants. A positive effect of treatment can be expected with a normal occlusal relationship of the jaws and a sufficient height of the alveolar ridge. A general treatment plan was drawn up for the patient based on the results of the examination, including therapeutic preparation of teeth before prosthetics. It was planned to install implants both directly into the sockets of the extracted teeth and into the intact alveolar bone. Orthopedic planning included determining the location of implants, the optimal height of artificial crowns and the possibility of hygienic care of the prosthesis. Surgical placement of implants was focused on the planned prosthetic construction. The operation was performed in compliance with the rules of asepsis and antisepsis in a surgical room (operating room). The main task of orthopedic treatment was the restoration of chewing function, which required the creation of optimal contact surfaces. Immediate loading is based on the production of an orthopedic structure with rigid fixation within the next 3 days after the operation.

Metal-plastic prostheses are comfortable orthopedic structures that can be easily corrected and repaired in the oral cavity, therefore they are used as temporary prostheses. Ceramic-metal or highly aesthetic, compatible with the soft tissues of the oral cavity, zirconium prostheses are made as permanent structures after 6 months.

Results and discussion .Patients were examined after a week, 1, 3, 6 months and a year. During the observation period, occlusion correction and professional oral hygiene were carried out. After 6 months, a mandatory control orthopantomography was performed; if necessary, patients were referred for 3D studies. The second stage of prosthetics was carried out after 6 months with the replacement of temporary structures with ceramic-metal ones. The main criteria by which the state of the dental implant in the bone tissue was assessed were: 1) the degree of implant mobility; 2) the presence of damage to bone tissue; 3) the degree and rate of bone atrophy; 4) condition of the mucous membrane adjacent to the implant; 5) the depth of the pocket between the implant and the mucosa; 6) the quality of the fit of the implant to adjacent teeth; 7) the effectiveness of the functional load; 8) the ratio of the implant and anatomical formations. When evaluating the quality criteria for the installation of dental implants in the postoperative period (7-14 days after surgery), subjective criteria were taken into account: pain from minor soreness to severe localized pain. When evaluating the quality criteria for the installation of dental implants (3-4 months after surgery), a subjective assessment of pain sensations was carried out; clinically determined the degree of soft tissue edema, inflammation in the area of implant placement, bleeding of the gingival mucosa during probing, controlled implant mobility, assessed the presence of plaque. When conducting radiation research methods, the degree of engraftment of the implant in the bone tissue was determined (orthopantomography, dental program or cone beam computed tomography). The criteria for radiodiagnosis were the following indicators: the bone tissue is tightly adjacent to the surface of the implant; lack of bone tissue in the area of the implant for two turns of thread; horizontal resorption of bone tissue by 1/2 of the implant length; vertical unilateral resorption of bone tissue. The results of the examination in the postoperative period (7-14 days) showed that in 55% of cases, patients experienced minor pain, in 45% - localized pain. The presence of soft tissue edema with localization in the area of implant installation was observed in 75% of cases, in 25% - edema in the area of implant installation and the mucous membrane of the alveolar process of the jaw. In 75% of cases, hyperemia of the mucous membrane in the area of the periodontal papilla was registered, in 25% - hyperemia of the marginal edge with bleeding during probing. An objective examination found that in 100% of cases, the mobility of the implants was not observed. Examination of the aesthetic condition of the dentition showed that the color and shape of the artificial crown is not broken. After the operation, in the control period of 3-4 months, there were no pain sensations, no inflammation was observed, the implants were

immobile, the bone tissue tightly adhered over the entire surface of the implant, the oral hygiene in the average according to the ONI-S index was satisfactory, signs of mucositis and peri-implantitis were not detected. In one case of two-stage implantation, osseointegration did not occur, vertical unilateral resorption of bone tissue was registered on the X-ray, pronounced implant mobility, edema and hyperemia of the gum and mucous membrane tissues were clinically determined, the implant was in the soft tissues and was removed. An assessment of the quality criteria for the installation of dental implants after 6 months showed that during a two-stage operation in the long term, the patients had no pain, no inflammation was observed, the implants were immobile, the bone tissue fit snugly over the entire surface of the implant. During a one-stage operation, pain and inflammation were also not observed, the implants were motionless, the bone tissue was tightly attached over the entire surface of the implant. The assessment of the aesthetic condition indicated that the color and shape of the artificial crowns were not disturbed, immovably fixed, and the occlusion was uniform. The analysis of the condition of the prostheses in the observation period from 6 months to 1 year after the operation indicated that the frequency of requests for implant removal due to the lack of osseointegration was 1.04% of cases. The use of basal implantation allows the installation of implants without exfoliation of the mucoperiosteal flap (transgingivally), as well as directly into the sockets of the extracted teeth immediately after their removal. This method is a minimally

invasive method of surgical treatment, which can significantly reduce the time of the postoperative period and the patient's disability.

The use of intraosseous implants for fixing dentures increases chewing activity by 19–44% compared to traditional removable prosthetics, and also allows almost complete restoration of motor and tonic activity of masticatory muscles.

References:

1. Ide S., Ide A. Nemedlennaya nagruzka. – Myunkhen, 2013. – 400 s.
2. Kitaev V.A. Kliniko-biokhimicheskaya otsenka rezul'tatov dental'noi implantatsii: Avtoref. dis. ... kand. med. nauk / V.A. Kitaev. – M., 2007. – 24 s.
3. Kulakov O.B. // Institut stomatologii. – 2003. – №1. – S.115–116.
4. Malanchuk V.A. Neposredstvennaya dental'naya implantatsiya / V.A. Malanchuk, E.A. Mamedov. – Kiev, 2008. – 157 s.
5. Paraskevich V. // Stomatologicheskii zhurnal. – 2000. – №4. – S.8–10.
6. Polupan P.V. // Med. alfavit (Stomatologiya №2). – 2014. – №7. – S.18–24.
7. Khobkek D.A., Uotson Z.M., Sizm L.D.D. Rukovodstvo po dental'noi implantologii. – M., 2010. – 223 s.
8. Kopp S., Kopp W. // JMOSI. – 2008. – Vol.7, N1. – P.116–122.